

DELAMINATION CRACKS ORIGINATING FROM TRANSVERSE
CRACKING IN CROSS-PLY LAMINATES UNDER VARIOUS
LOADINGS

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ABSTRACT

Based upon the Stroh formalism for anisotropic elastic materials and upon the method of eigenfunction expansion, the stress redistribution due to delamination cracks originating from transverse cracking is examined for cross-ply laminates under plane strain extension, plane strain bending and antiplane shear. The structure of solution in the form of series expansion is determined from the eigenvalue equation resulting from appropriate near-field conditions. To complete the solution, use is made of the boundary collocation method or the singular hybrid finite element method. The fracture mechanics parameters, such as, stress intensity factors and energy release rates are calculated, and the stability of crack growth is examined for varying ratios of ply thickness in terms of the energy release rate.

KEYWORDS: Boundary collocation method; Hybrid finite element method; stress intensity factors; energy release rates; stability.

1. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM AND BASIC EQUATIONS

Consider cross-ply composite laminates, $[90/0]_s$, subjected to extension, bending or antiplane shear. As the load increases, there will occur numerous transverse cracks running parallel to the fiber orientation of the 90° ply, with an approximately uniform spacing along the length of the laminates. These cracks, terminating perpendicularly to the ply interface because of the stronger 0° ply, tend to develop into delamination cracks along the interface as the load increases further. We will examine fracture behavior of the laminate containing such interfacial cracks under plane strain extension, plane strain bending and antiplane shear. To simplify the problem, we assume that the cracks are uniformly arranged with the configuration symmetric about the mid-plane, as shown in Fig.1, so that the overall arrangement is obtained by repetition of the representative unit cell. We take a rectangular Cartesian coordinate system with origin at one of the crack tip. We choose the x_1 axis to be along the length of composite laminates while the x_2 axis is taken to be along the direction of the laminate thickness, and then the x_3 axis becomes along the laminate width, which is parallel to the cracks(see Fig.1). Each ply of the composite laminates lies in a plane parallel to the x_1 - x_3 plane, and the ply

Fig. 1. Delamination cracks originating from transverse cracking in $[90/0]_s$ under plane strain bending, plane strain extension and antiplane shear ($\epsilon_0 = \bar{u}/b$, $\gamma_0 = \bar{w}/b$)

orientation θ is defined to be the counterclockwise angle, viewed from the top, that the fiber direction makes with the x_1 axis. We assume that the laminate dimension in the x_3 direction (laminate width) is sufficiently large compared with the laminate thickness and that the laminate is assumed to be in the state of plane strain extension, plane strain bending and antiplane shear on the x_1 - x_2 plane. Let $u_i, \sigma_{ij}, \epsilon_{ij}$ denote the Cartesian components of displacement, stress and strain, respectively. For deformations that depend upon two coordinates x_1 and x_2 only, we have the governing equations of equilibrium equation, strain-displacement relation stress-strain relation :

$$\sigma_{i1,1} + \sigma_{i2,2} = 0, \quad \epsilon_{ij} = (u_{i,j} + u_{j,i}) / 2, \quad \sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl} \epsilon_{kl}, \quad (1.a,b,c)$$

where C_{ijkl} are the 4-th order stiffness tensor, and comma indicates the partial differentiation with respect to x_i . Introducing the "collapsed" representation, we may write the stress-strain relation as

$$\sigma_i = C_{ij} \epsilon_j, \quad \epsilon_i = S_{ij} \sigma_j, \quad (2.a,b)$$

where C_{ij} and S_{ij} are the stiffness and the compliance matrix, and the two indices for the stress and the engineering strain are collapsed as follows : (1,1) \rightarrow (1), (2,2) \rightarrow (2), (3,3) \rightarrow (3), (2,3) \rightarrow (4), (1,3) \rightarrow (5), (1,2) \rightarrow (6). For orthotropic materials likes $[90/0]_s$, and $[0/90]_s$ laminates, we have

$$C_{14} = C_{15} = C_{16} = C_{24} = C_{25} = C_{26} = C_{34} = C_{35} = C_{36} = C_{45} = C_{46} = C_{56} = 0. \quad (3)$$

For such materials, the displacement component u_3 is decoupled from u_1, u_2 , that is, the antiplane shear is decoupled from the plane strain deformation. To determine the solution structure for the present problem, we use the so-called Stroh formalism[1].

Fig.2. Typical mesh configuration for the plane strain extension, plane strain bending and antiplane shear of $[90/0]_s$ laminates

Following Ting[1], we can show that the general solution takes the form for the present problem,

$$u_\alpha = v_{\alpha k} f(z_k), \quad z_k = x_1 + \mu_k x_2 \quad (k=1,2,3,4) \tag{4.a,b}$$

$$\sigma_{\alpha\beta} = \tau_{\alpha\beta k} \frac{df(z_k)}{dz_k}, \quad \tau_{\alpha\beta k} = (C_{\alpha\beta\gamma 1} + \mu_k C_{\alpha\beta\gamma 2}) v_{\gamma k} \text{ for plane strain extension and bending} \tag{4.c,d}$$

$$u_3 = v_{3\ell} g(\zeta_\ell), \quad \zeta_\ell = x_1 + v_\ell x_2 \quad (\ell = 1,2) \tag{5.a,b}$$

$$\sigma_{3\alpha} = \tau_{3\alpha\ell} \frac{dg(\zeta_\ell)}{d\zeta_\ell}, \quad \tau_{3\alpha\ell} = (C_{3\alpha 31} + v_\ell C_{3\alpha 32}) v_{3\ell} \text{ for antiplane shear,} \tag{5.c,d}$$

where summation is implied on repeated Greek indices; μ_k, v_ℓ are the eigenvalues to be determined, and $f(z_k), g(\zeta_\ell)$ are functions of z_k, ζ_ℓ . Substituting equations (4.c) and (5.c) into equation (1.a), we obtain the equations for plane strain extension and bending, and antiplane shear:

$$D_{\alpha\beta}(\mu_k) v_{\beta k} = 0, \quad D_{\alpha\beta}(\mu_k) = C_{\alpha 1\beta 1} + \mu_k (C_{\alpha 1\beta 2} + C_{\alpha 2\beta 1}) + \mu_k^2 C_{\alpha 2\beta 2}, \tag{6.a,b}$$

$$D_{33}(v_\ell) v_3 = 0, \quad D_{33}(v_\ell) = C_{3131} + v_\ell (C_{3132} + C_{3231}) + v_\ell^2 C_{3232}. \tag{6.c,d}$$

For the existence of nontrivial solutions, we have

$$\det[D_{\alpha\beta}(\mu_k)] = |D_{\alpha\beta}(\mu_k)| = 0, \quad \det[D_{33}(v_\ell)] = |D_{33}(v_\ell)| = 0, \tag{7.a,b}$$

and the solutions of the quartic equation and the quadratic equation yield the two pairs of complex conjugate eigenvalues

$$\bar{\mu}_{\alpha+2} = \mu_{\alpha} \quad (\alpha=1,2), \quad v_1 = v_2. \quad (8.a,b)$$

2. ASYMPTOTIC EIGENFUNCTION EXPANSION

We assume the power type eigenfunction for $f(z_k)$, $g(\zeta_l)$ as given by Ting[1]

$$f(z_k) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C_{kn} z_k^{\delta_n+1} / (\delta_n+1), \quad g(\zeta_l) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} D_{ln} \zeta_l^{\delta_n+1} / (\delta_n+1), \quad (9.a,b)$$

(k=1,2,3, 4) (l = 1, 2)

which leads to the expression for the displacement and stress field

$$u_{\alpha}^{(m)} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C_{kn}^{(m)} v_{\alpha k}^{(m)} z_k^{(m)\delta_n+1} / (\delta_n+1), \quad \sigma_{\alpha\beta}^{(m)} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C_{kn}^{(m)} \tau_{\alpha\beta k}^{(m)} z_k^{(m)\delta_n} \quad (10.a,b)$$

(k=1,2,3, 4)

$$u_3^{(m)} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} D_{ln}^{(m)} v_{3l}^{(m)} \zeta_l^{(m)\delta_n+1} / (\delta_n+1), \quad \sigma_{3\alpha}^{(m)} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} D_{ln}^{(m)} \tau_{3\alpha l}^{(m)} \zeta_l^{(m)\delta_n} \quad (l = 1,2) \quad (10.c,d)$$

where the superscript $m=1,2$ indicates one of the two different plies, respectively. Here the eigenvalues δ_n are to be determined from the so called "near-field" conditions around the crack tip, including the traction or displacement conditions on the crack surface and on the ply interface. The coefficients C_{kn} or D_{ln} are dependent upon the associated eigenvalues δ_n , and it can be determined within an arbitrary constant when δ_n is obtained. We assume that the two plies are rigidly bonded along the rest of the ply interface. Then the near field conditions for the plane strain extension and bending may be written as

$$\sigma_{22}^{(1)}(x_1, 0^+) = \sigma_{22}^{(2)}(x_1, 0^-) = 0, \quad \sigma_{12}^{(1)}(x_1, 0^+) = \sigma_{12}^{(2)}(x_1, 0^-) = 0 \quad (11.a,b)$$

(on the crack surface, $x_1 \leq 0$),

$$[\sigma_{22}(x_1, 0)] = [\sigma_{12}(x_1, 0)] = 0, \quad [u_1(x_1, 0)] = [u_2(x_1, 0)] = 0 \quad (12.a,b)$$

(on the interface, $x_1 \geq 0$),

where the bracket [] denotes the discontinuity of the quantity in it across the ply interface, for example, $[\sigma_{22}(x_1, 0)] = \sigma_{22}^{(1)}(x_1, 0^+) - \sigma_{22}^{(2)}(x_1, 0^-)$. The similar conditions can be written for the antiplane shear, which is omitted here. To take only the real part of equations (10.a,b) for convenience, we may introduce, say for $C_{kn}^{(\alpha)}$,

$$C_{kn}^{(\alpha)} = 1/2(\gamma_{1v} - i\gamma_{2v})b_{kn}^{(\alpha)} \quad \text{for complex } \delta_n, \quad \text{Im}[\delta_n] > 0$$

$$C_{kn}^{(\alpha)} = 1/2 \gamma_{3v} b_{kn}^{(\alpha)} \quad \text{for real } \delta_n, \quad (13)$$

where $b_{kn}^{(\alpha)}$ is obtained from the foregoing near-field conditions and γ_{1v} , γ_{2v} , γ_{3v} are constants to be determined from the remote boundary conditions through matching with the aid of numerical techniques such as the boundary collocation method and the hybrid F.E.M..

Fig. 3. Energy release rate versus the length of delamination crack under a fixed load for bending, extension and antiplane shear in $[90/0]_s$

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we determine the unknown free constant $\gamma_{1v}, \gamma_{2v}, \gamma_{3v}$ through the boundary collocation method or the hybrid F.E.M to complete the solution. We will discuss the nature of near-tip singular fields in terms of stress intensity, and the fracture behavior of delamination cracks, including the stability of crack growth and the effects of ply thickness upon the energy release rates. For numerical computation, we use the following material data for the graphite epoxy T300/5208,

$$E_L=134 \text{ GPa} , E_T =E_Z=10.2 \text{ GPa} , G_{LT}=G_{LZ}=5.52 \text{ GPa} , G_{TZ}=3.43 \text{ GPa}$$

$$\nu_{LT} = \nu_{LZ} = 0.3 , \nu_{TZ} = 0.49 .$$

To determine the free constants and thereby complete the solution, we match the near-field solution (10.a,c) with the remote boundary conditions, comprising the remaining conditions other than the near-field conditions, through boundary collocation method, or through singular hybrid F.E.M., wherein the crack tip region is modeled as a singular element into which the asymptotic solution is embedded, and the other region as the displacement-based regular finite elements (Fig.2). The details of such formulation are not described here, but interested readers may be referred to [2,3]. To confirm the solution, the hybrid F.E.M. solution is compared with the boundary collocation solution in terms of the stress intensity factor for the loading of extension and antiplane shear in Table 1. We find an excellent agreement between the two solutions. Fig.3 shows the stability of crack growth in terms of energy release rates under a fixed load condition for the plane strain bending, the plane strain extension and

Table I. Comparison of two methods:

unit : [GPa(m)^{1/2}]

	Antiplane shear		Pure bending		extension		
	(No. of eigenvalues)	K_{II}/Y_0	K_I/θ_0	K_{II}/θ_0	(No. of eigenvalues)	K_I/E_0	K_{II}/E_0
Collocation method	40	-1.0634			51	2.6514	3.0656
(100 collocation station)	60	-1.0634	-	-	63	2.7016	3.0511
	80	-1.0634	-	-	110	2.7207	3.0291
	(No. of elements)		(No. of elements)		(No. of elements)		
Hybrid F.E.M	41	-1.0523	39	1.3265 1.0445	41	2.7576	3.1062
(15 eigenvalues)	47	-1.0615	47	1.3274 1.0442	53	2.7999	3.1441
	53	-1.0629	55	1.3277 1.0441	71	2.7249	3.1511

the antiplane shear, respectively. It reveals important features regarding the growth of delamination cracks originating from transverse cracking in cross-ply laminates. When we assume the failure criterion based upon the critical energy release rate, $G=G_C$ (G_C is a material constant), we see that for extension and bending any delamination crack will undergo unstable growth until the crack length reaches a critical value associated with the maximum G , and it will continue to grow under a fixed loading until the energy release rate decrease to the critical value G_C . Thus there exists an inherently built-in crack arrest mechanism for the plane strain extension and bending. For the antiplane shear, on the other hand, G versus crack length curve is relatively flat other than large values of G for vanishing crack length. It is worthwhile to note that energy release rate does not go to zero for vanishing crack length under antiplane shear because the stress singularity for the transverse cracks (which is obtained as the delamination cracks vanish) is stronger than the square root singularity under the antiplane shear [4].

The stress singularity is oscillatory for the opened interfacial cracks and therefore physically inadmissible interpenetration occurs as r goes to zero. To rectify such a shortcoming, Comninou [5] proposed a new interfacial crack model for dissimilar isotropic materials, wherein the partially closed crack faces are in frictionless contact near the tips, and Wang and Choi [6] extended such a partially closed crack model to the case of dissimilar anisotropic materials. However, the zone of interpenetration is negligibly small in a fully opened model, and the stress fields, except for the near tip region are almost the same for the two models. Then the J -integral calculated along a path away from the crack tip will be almost the same for the two models and the present energy release rate G calculated by Irwin's virtual crack extension concept is the same as J calculated as above, which is equivalent to the energy release rate calculated by way of the change of global strain energy. As far as G_C criterion is considered, the two models yield almost the same G and it is sufficient to consider an opened crack model alone for the present purpose.

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